

POLICY CONFERENCE

UNLOCKING CIRCULARITY AND
MARKET POTENTIAL FROM WOOD WASTE
25 MARCH 2026, BRUSSELS

THE CIRCULAR ECONOMY ACT

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Circular Economy Act

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Clean Industrial Deal

A plan for EU competitiveness and decarbonisation

You will work with the Commissioner for Environment, Water Resilience and a Competitive Circular Economy to present the **Circular Economy Act**, helping to create market demand for secondary materials and a single market for waste, notably in relation to critical raw materials.

As part of your work in contributing to the Clean Industrial Deal, you will lead, with the Executive Vice-President for Prosperity and Industrial Strategy, on a **Circular Economy Act** with measures to create market demand for secondary materials and establish a single market for waste, notably in relation to critical raw materials.

A more circular and resilient economy

Working to decarbonise our economy will be part of our continued shift to a more sustainable pattern of production and consumption, retaining the value of resources in our economy for longer.

This will be the purpose of a new **Circular Economy Act**, helping to create market demand for secondary materials and a single market for waste, notably in relation to critical raw materials.

Main Objectives of the CEA

- Accelerate the EU's transition towards a circular economy and **double the circular material use** rate (from 12.2% in 2025 to 24% by 2030, in line with the Clean Industrial Deal).
- Reduce the **dependency on imports** of key raw materials.
- Have simple, clear and digital rules for secondary raw materials, to ensure a level playing field across the Single Market.
- Increase the quantity of **separately collected waste**, as well as the quantity and quality of secondary raw materials.
- Reduce waste from being generated.

CEA Structure

The CEA will attempt to **update and streamline the current acquis**, with a particular focus on two axis:

- The Waste Framework Directive and the Landfill Directive
- The Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE) Directive

 Centre of gravity of assessment

Circular Economy Act

Demand

Circularity in public procurement

Industrial symbiosis

Supply

Streamline EPR schemes

End of Waste criteria

Restriction of materials export

Digital pre-demolition inventory

A stylized illustration of a wooden bridge with a curved railing, spanning a stream. The stream is surrounded by green grass, rocks, and small white flowers. The background is a light blue sky with a few white clouds.

Single Market for secondary materials

Public Consultation

- Consultation period: 1 August - 6 November 2025
- Total of valid feedback instances received: **820**

Call for evidence

- Consultation period: 1 August - 6 November 2025
- Total of valid feedback instances received: **962**

Detailed Targeted Stakeholder Consultation

- Consultation period: 6 November – 4 December 2025
- Total of valid feedback instances received: avg. **166** (final number tbc)

SME Panel (focus on 5 topics)

- Consultation period: 9 December 2025 – 16 March 2026
- Translated in all EU languages from 13 January 2026

Final Stakeholder Workshop

- Indicative timeline: end of April 2026 (exact date tbc)

Thank you

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